

Beliefs and Practices Among Mothers Regarding Immunization - A Hospital Based Study

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ABSTRACT

During this cross sectional study, 200 mothers who had a live baby of less than one year were interviewed in Pediatric OPD of a tertiary care hospital with the help of pre-validated, semi-structured questionnaire regarding immunization coverage for primary vaccination and assessment of their beliefs and practices. Present study found that 92.5% of the infants were completely immunized for the age, 5.5 % were partially immunized and 2.0% were un-immunized at the time of interview. Mothers preferred Primary Health Centre (PHC) or Anganwadi over other hospitals for vaccination. Most of the mothers maintained vaccination card. Main reasons for failure to vaccinate were lack of knowledge of immunization schedule and infant's illness when vaccine dose was due. All the mothers (100%) believed that immunization is important and beneficial for the child and 60.5% of mothers had the knowledge regarding fever as the side effect of vaccination for which they gave Syrup Paracetamol. As it was a hospital based survey, we found infants with high vaccination coverage for the age. Most of the mothers showed positive attitude and desirable practices regarding primary vaccination.

KEY WORDS: beliefs; immunization; infants; practices; mothers

INTRODUCTION:

Vaccines have the power not only to save lives but giving children the chance to grow up healthy. Immunization is a proven cost effective intervention for controlling and eliminating life-threatening infectious diseases in all age groups from various diseases including diphtheria, tetanus, pertussis and measles. Since the time of Edward Jenner, vaccination has controlled nine major diseases at least in parts of the world; they are- small pox, diphtheria, tetanus, yellow fever, pertussis, poliomyelitis, measles, mumps and rubella. In case of small pox, the dream of eradication has come true. We are moving towards eradication of polio from the world. Polio has been eradicated from India and now we are looking forward for eradication of measles.

In 1985, Universal Immunization Program was started in India with an aim of achieving at least

85% coverage of primary immunization in infants with 3 doses of DPT & OPV, one dose of BCG and one dose of Measles by 1990.^[1] As per National Family Health Survey (NFHS-3) data, only 44 % of infants in India are fully immunized which is much less than desired goal of 85% but is slightly higher than the coverage as per NFHS-2 (42%).^[2]

In India, large part of population lives in rural areas, where mothers are mostly illiterate and has numerous myths about vaccination. Immunization coverage among tribal areas is also low because of difficult accessibility and poor acceptability due to the various cultural beliefs. The situation of under immunization is not only in the rural or tribal areas but also in the urban areas because of migration and developing pockets of slums. People are living in these pockets with unprecedented poverty, illiteracy, overcrowding and large burden of diseases.^[3] All these factors result in children being either unimmunized or partially immunized posing serious policy concern.

The aim of our study was to assess vaccination coverage, beliefs and practices of mothers who had a live baby of less than one year regarding

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immunization. We also tried to identify the existing gaps in awareness, knowledge and practices that need to be fulfilled to achieve the immunization targets.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:

A cross sectional descriptive study was carried out to assess vaccination coverage, beliefs and practices of mothers regarding immunization. The study was carried out in Pediatric Department of a tertiary care hospital attached to medical college in central India. A total of 200 children below one year were selected from outpatient department by convenient sampling after taking informed written consent from the mothers. Predesigned and pretested pro-forma was used to collect information regarding socio-demographic profile, vaccination status of their infants and their beliefs and practices regarding infant vaccination. Data was collected by one to one interview of mothers. Data was analyzed by using SPSS 19 and appropriate test were applied where required.

Inclusion criteria for the study were: (a) mothers who had live baby of less than one year of age (at the time of interview); (b) mothers who were willing to participate in the study. Exclusion criteria for the study were: (a) mothers who had live baby of more one year of age; (b) mothers who did not give consent for the study. This study was undertaken after getting approved by institutional research advisory committee (RAC) and Institutional Ethics Committee (IEC).

RESULTS:

Table 1 shows demographic profile of mothers. Hindu family predominates and most of the mothers were either illiterate or educated up to primary level only. Two hundred mothers having babies less than 12 months old were interviewed. Out of 200 infants, 110 were males and 90 were females. Present study found that 92.5% of the infants were completely immunized for the age, 5.5 % were partially immunized and 2.0% were un-immunized at the time of interview. Mothers preferred PHC/ Anganwadi over government/ private hospitals for vaccination. Most of the mothers maintained vaccination card (Table 2).

Main reasons for non immunization and partial immunization were poor knowledge of immunization schedule and infants' illness when vaccine dose was due (Table 3). All mothers (100%)

Table 1: Socio-demographic profile of mothers

S.No	Factors	Category	N = 200	%
1.	Age (Year)	<25	122	61
		>25	78	39
2.	Caste	SC	18	9.0
		ST	23	11.5
		OBC	42	21
		Others	117	58.5
3.	Religion	Hindu	171	85.5
		Muslim	25	12.5
		Sikhs	3	1.5
		Christian	1	0.5
4.	Education	Illiterate	60	30
		Primary	75	37.5
		Secondary	32	16
		Graduation	14	7.0
		Post Graduate	19	9.5
5.	Type of Family	Nuclear	111	55.5
		Joint	88	44
		Separated	1	0.5
6.	Family Income/Month	<2000	2	1.0
		2000 -4000	68	34
		>4000	130	65
7.	No. of Siblings	0	50	25
		1	68	34
		2	53	26.5
		>2	29	14.5

believed that immunization is important and beneficial for their children. Most of them knew that immunization is to be started at birth. Approximately half of them knew the names of all the vaccines given under national immunization schedule (Table 4). Table 5 shows that 60.5% of mothers had the knowledge regarding fever as the side effect of vaccination and they gave Syrup Paracetamol for it.

DISCUSSION:

As per National Family Health Survey (NFHS -3) data, only 44 % of infants in India are fully immunized. It is further less in Madhya Pradesh (40.3%).^[4] In the present study, immunization

Table 2. Vaccination status of infants

	N = 200	%
1 VACCINATION STATUS		
Fully vaccinated for their age	185	92.5
Partially vaccinated for their age.	11	5.5
Not vaccinated at all	4	2.0
2 PLACE OF VACCINATION		
At home (by ANMs)	6	3.0
At PHC/Anganwadi	127	63.5
Government hospitals	54	27
Private hospitals /clinics	13	6.5
3 MAINTAINENCE OF VACCINATION CARD		
Yes	184	92
No	16	8.0

Table 3. Reasons for partial immunization or non-immunization.

S. No.	Factors causing incomplete immunization	N = 15	%
1	Poor awareness of immunization schedule	6	40
2	Mothers too busy	2	13.33
3	Objection by elder member of the family	1	6.66
4	Child was ill when vaccination was due	5	33.33
5	Place of immunization too far from home	1	6.66

coverage for the age (at the time of interview) is quite satisfactory as fully immunized infants were 92.5% and very few infants were totally un-immunized (2%

Table 4. Knowledge of mothers regarding vaccines

	N = 200	%
1 How many mothers knew that vaccination is must for their baby?		
200	100	
2 How many mothers knew that the first vaccination is given at birth?		
180	90	
3 How many mothers knew the name of various vaccines covered in EPI		
Knowing names of all vaccines	95	47.5
Knowing names of few vaccines.	35	17.5
Not knowing the name of any vaccine	70	35

Table 5. Knowledge regarding treatment of side effects due to vaccines:

	N=200	%
It does not require any treatment.	10	5.0
I give tapid sponging for fever	24	12
I go to doctor if any side effect occurs	45	22.5
I give Syrup Paracetamol for fever on my own	121	60.5

in present study as compared to 5% in MP according to NFHS-3). This high rate of vaccine coverage is comparable to results documented by Singh et al^[5], Shamila hamid et al^[6] and Basaleem et al.^[7]

A study conducted during Aug 2008 to Jan 2009 by Joshi et al reported that approximately 50% of children were fully immunized while 27.5% were partially immunized and 22.5% were not immunized at all.^[8] In a similar study conducted in September, 2000 on 294 children between ages of 12-24 months living in slums of Surat, only 25% were fully immunized, 51.7% were partially immunized and 23.1% were unimmunized.^[9]

Immunization coverage assessment studies by Sheth et al,^[10] Vikram et al^[11] and Kadri et al^[12] have shown that more than 60% of children were fully immunized. Major reasons for not immunizing the child were lack of awareness of the need of immunization and lack of availability of services in rural areas. Whereas in present study, two main reasons of missed immunization were poor awareness of mothers regarding vaccines covered in National Immunization Schedule and infants' illness when next vaccine was scheduled.

Mothers preferred government setup either Aganwadi, PHC or government hospitals for vaccinating their infants as also reported by Hamid et al.^[6] More than 90% of mothers in present study could reproduce the vaccination card as against 25.4% , an overall data from NFHS- 3 for whole of MP.^[4]

Being it a hospital based survey is the limitation of present study. Here we have surveyed infants who had come to Pediatric OPD for well baby clinic or for any minor illness. High vaccination coverage found in present study could be because of inclusion of younger babies at the time of maternal interview even before completion of primary vaccination.

CONCLUSION:

Though the knowledge and beliefs of the mothers and vaccination coverage (for the age) of infants was found good in present study, it can be further improved by imparting awareness to general public through regular health education programs by doctors, paramedics and health workers. Media can also play a big role (*Do Boond Jindagi Ki*). It can be achieved by sincere efforts of all health care professionals and policy makers.

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